

Surveying Students Sports Interest as a Basis to Improve the Student Sports Programs of San Isidro College

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ABSTRACT

Sports are crucial for students' physical health, mental well-being, and social development, fostering essential life skills and a sense of community. Despite their benefits, more comprehensive studies on student sports interests need to be conducted, highlighting the need for inclusive research to develop effective sports programs that cater to all student preferences. The study utilized a descriptive research design, systematic sampling, and an online survey method. Data was gathered from 795 college students, ensuring a diverse and representative sample. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data, providing comprehensive insights into students' sports interests. The result shows strong student interest in sports and the need for supportive programs to build skills and confidence. Popular sports like badminton and volleyball could be prioritized, with efforts to increase participation in less frequent and higher-level competitions. Understanding and addressing student expectations and self-perceptions are crucial for effective sports program development. To maximize student participation and interest in sports, the study recommends establishing specialized training programs and sports clinics for high-interest sports like badminton and volleyball, along with regular competitions and recreational play opportunities. Additionally, resources could be allocated to improve sports facilities and hire qualified coaches while promoting less popular sports to ensure a diverse and inclusive sports environment.

Keywords: *athlete, sports, sports interest, student athlete*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Sports play a crucial role in the lives of students, contributing significantly to their physical health (Pituk & Cagas, 2019), mental well-being (Hernani et al., 2022), and social development (Montecalbo-Ignacio et al., 2017). Engaging in sports helps students develop essential life skills such as teamwork (Martinez, 2023), leadership (Cipriano et al., 2024), discipline (Gacria & Subia,

2019), and resilience (Orines et al., 2023). Furthermore, incorporating sports into the educational curriculum supports the holistic development of students, ensuring they grow into well-rounded individuals. The importance of sports extends beyond physical fitness, fostering a sense of community and belonging, and providing a productive outlet for stress and anxiety (Liad, 2020).

Despite the recognized benefits of sports, more comprehensive studies need to survey students' specific interests in various sports activities. Most existing research focuses on popular sports like basketball and volleyball, often overshadowing other sports that might attract student interest (Blanco, 2016; Gems, 2023). This limited scope must provide a complete picture of student sports preferences, potentially neglecting lesser-known sports that could significantly contribute to student engagement and development (Corcuera & Bernardo, 2024).

Understanding that students have diverse interests in sports, this study seeks to address the need for a more inclusive examination of student sports preferences. By exploring a broader range of sports, the study aims to fill the empirical gap in existing research concerning student interest in sports (Lagrio et al., 2017). Recognizing these varied interests is crucial for developing effective sports programs catering to all students, promoting greater participation, and reaping the holistic benefits of sports involvement (Martin et al., 2016; Tabuena, 2020; Cruz, 2022).

This study aims to conduct a comprehensive survey of student sports interests, encompassing various sports activities beyond sports, providing a more detailed understanding of student preferences and supporting the development of inclusive sports programs that encourage participation from all students.

Theoretical Framework

The study is grounded in the Expectancy Theory (Vroom, 2005), which posits that individuals are motivated to engage in behaviors when they expect their efforts will lead to desired outcomes. In the context of this study, Expectancy Theory suggests that understanding students' sports interests can enhance their motivation to participate in sports programs. By surveying students' preferences, the study identifies which sports activities they are most likely to engage in, thereby informing the development of sports programs that align with their interests and expectations. The approach ensures that sports programs are tailored to meet student's desires, increasing their participation and the overall effectiveness of these programs in promoting physical health and holistic development.

Figure 1.
Schematic diagram of the study

The independent variable directly influences the dependent variable, Sports Programs for College Students. By collecting data on students' sports preferences through the survey, educators and program developers gain insights into which sports appeal most to the student body. This information is then used to design sports programs that reflect these interests, ensuring higher

levels of engagement and participation. Aligning sports programs with student preferences maximizes the possibility that students will participate in and benefit from the programs.

Statement of the Problem

Addressing the gap in current research, the study aimed to survey the broad spectrum of sports to enhance student engagement and be a basis for a student sports program for the institution. Specifically, it sought to answer the following question:

1. What is the student's engagement in sports and sports-related events?
2. What are the sports that the students are interested in participating and preferred by the students to engage in?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive research design (Dulock, 1993), which is particularly well-suited for this type of investigation as it allows for an in-depth examination of the various sports interests among college students. The design systematically describes the population's characteristics by collecting detailed information on their preferences, participation levels, and motivations regarding different sports. The descriptive nature of the study ensures that the data collected is comprehensive and representative of the diverse interests within the student body, providing valuable insights that can be used to develop tailored sports programs (Siedlecki, 2020).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sampling procedure for this study followed a systematic approach (Madow & Madow, 1994), initially grouping college students into strata based on their academic courses. Within each stratum, purposive sampling is then employed to select participants who are representative of the broader student population in terms of gender, year of study, and existing sports participation. This dual-layered sampling technique ensures that the sample is comprehensive and specific, capturing diverse interests across different academic disciplines while focusing on relevant subgroups. This approach enhances the study's ability to generate accurate and generalizable findings about student sports interests (Neyman, 1992).

Table 1.
Demographic profile of the respondents (N=795)

Demographic		f	%
Sex	Male	307	38.62
	Female	488	61.38
Year	First Year	377	47.42
	Second Year	228	28.68
	Third Year	115	14.47
	Fourth Year	75	9.43

Table 1.
Demographic profile of the respondents (N=795) (Cont)

Demographic		f	%
Course	AB	41	5.16
	BEED	54	6.79
	BSED	104	13.08
	BSBA	64	8.05
	BSOA	18	2.26
	BSA	41	5.16
	BSCE	99	12.45
	BSIT	52	6.54
	BSN/BSM	322	40.50

The study sample consists of 795 college students, 307 males, and 488 females, from first-year to fourth-year students. This distribution is advantageous as it reflects the demographic composition of the student population, ensuring that the findings represent various age groups, gender identities, and academic levels. Such a diverse sample allows for a thorough analysis of sports interests across different segments of the student body, providing a holistic view of the factors influencing sports participation.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data for the study was gathered using an online survey method (Toepoel, 2017), ensuring ease of access and participation for all students. The survey was distributed through the college's online system, and students were invited to participate. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, detailing the study's purpose, procedures, and data privacy measures to ensure ethical standards were met. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, with data being securely stored and only used for research purposes. The survey included questions designed to capture a wide range of information about students' sports interests, including the types of sports they prefer, frequency of participation, and reasons for their choices.

Data Analysis

The study employed descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation, to analyze the collected data. These statistical methods summarized and described the central tendencies and variability in students' sports interests. The study identified the average level of interest in different sports, while the standard deviation provided insights into the diversity of student preferences. The approach clearly and concisely represented the data, highlighting key trends and patterns in student sports interests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students Engagement in Sports and Sports-Related Events

Table 2 presents an analysis of students' self-evaluation regarding their involvement and participation in sports, including both frequency and percentage distributions.

Table 2.
Self-evaluation of students in sports (N=795)

Sport Involvement	Response					
	Yes		No		Not Sure	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Play Sports	524	65.91	271	34.09	-	-
Consider themselves Good at Sports	351	44.15	388	48.81	56	7.04
Participated in School Sports Competition	438	55.09	357	44.91	-	-

The data in Table 2 reveals that 65.91% of the students play sports, while 34.09% do not engage in sports activities. The significant majority indicates a strong overall interest in sports among students, suggesting that sports programs can engage a large portion of the student population (Liad, 2020). Students will likely participate in sports when they believe their efforts will lead to valued outcomes, such as improved physical health, social connections, or personal enjoyment. The high percentage of students already involved in sports implies that many students recognize these benefits and expect positive results from their participation (Martin et al., 2016).

Additionally, Table 2 shows that 44.15% of students consider themselves good at sports, 48.81% believe they are not, and 7.04% need to be aware of their abilities. This distribution highlights a nearly equal split in self-perception of sports competence (Martin et al., 2016). Students' participation in sports is influenced by their self-assessment of ability, which affects their expectations of success and the rewards they might achieve (Cruz, 2022). The high percentage of students who view themselves as not good at sports may indicate a need for supportive programs that build confidence and skills, thus increasing the likelihood of participation by aligning effort with achievable and valued outcomes (Garcia, 2022).

Moreover, the data in Table 2 indicates that 55.09% of students have participated in school sports competitions, while 44.91% have not. The result shows that more than half of the students have some experience with competitive sports, which can enhance their motivation and expectations of future participation (Tabuena, 2020). Past competition success can boost students' confidence and their expectation that continued participation will lead to further rewards. For students who need more competitive experience, creating opportunities for involvement in less formal, more inclusive competitions could help bridge this gap and enhance their expectancy of positive outcomes (Balite & Robles, 2020; Garcia, 2022).

Table 3 provides an overview of the frequency with which students engage in sports-related activities.

Table 3.
Students' frequency in participating in sports related activities (N=795)

Sport Participation	f	%
Daily	44	5.53
Thrice a Week	78	9.81
Twice a Week	114	14.34
Once a Week	313	39.37
Occasional Participation	246	30.94

Table 3 reveals that 5.53% of students practice sports daily, 9.81% practice three times a week, 14.34% practice twice a week, 39.37% practice at least once a week, and 30.94% practice occasionally. The data indicates that while a significant portion of students practice sports regularly, many engage in sports only occasionally. The frequency of practice is likely linked to the students' perceived effort and the expected outcomes (Cruz, 2022). Programs that encourage regular practice by highlighting the benefits and making practice sessions more accessible and enjoyable could help increase the overall frequency of participation (Marin et al., 2016; Lagrio et al., 2017).

Table 4 provides an overview of students' participation in sports competitions outside of college events.

Table 4.

Students' participation in sports related competition outside school (N=795)

Participation Experience	f	%
Local competitions	239	30.06
Provincial competitions	28	3.52
Regional competitions	50	6.29
National competitions	33	4.15
International competitions	1	0.13
None	444	55.85

Table 4 shows that 30.06% of students have participated in local sports competitions (i.e. Barangay, City, or Municipal level), 3.52% in provincial competitions (i.e. Interschool Sport Competition or Division Meet), 6.26% in regional competitions (Regional Meet or PRISAA), 4.15% in national competitions (i.e. Palarong Pambansa, Batang Pinoy, PRISAA National Games, or others), and 0.13% in international competitions (i.e. SEA Games or Asian Games). The result indicates that while many students participate in local events, participation drops significantly at higher levels. The decrease in higher-level participation may be due to higher perceived challenges and lower expected success. To address this, institutions could provide more support and training for students aspiring to compete at higher levels, increasing their confidence and expectation of success (Lagrio et al., 2017; Tabuena, 2020; Garcia, 2022).

Sports Interest of the Students'

Table 5 summarizes the sports interests of the surveyed students, presenting data on frequency, percentages, and rankings to illustrate the relative popularity of different sports.

Table 5.
Sport interest of the surveyed students (N=795)

Sport	f	%	Rank
Badminton	342	43.02	1
Volleyball	314	39.50	2
Basketball	197	24.78	3
Softball	112	14.09	4
Table Tennis	86	10.82	5
Swimming	77	9.69	6
Dart	76	9.56	7
Chess	73	9.18	8
Archery	70	8.81	9
Running Sprint	51	6.42	10
Taekwondo	48	6.04	11
Baseball	47	5.91	12
Football	39	4.91	13
Basketball3x3	37	4.65	14
Beach Volley	36	4.53	15
Boxing	34	4.28	16
Lawn Tennis	33	4.15	17
Sepak Takraw	28	3.52	18
Karate-Do	27	3.40	19
Running Middle Distance	21	2.64	20
E-Sports	16	2.01	21
Throwing Events	16	2.01	21
Judo	15	1.89	22
Weightlifting	15	1.89	22
Jumping Events	14	1.76	23
Running Long Distance	13	1.64	24
Frisbee	6	0.75	25
Billiard	2	0.25	26
Gymnastics	1	0.13	27

Table 5 indicates that 43.02% of students show interest in badminton (ranked first), 39.50% in volleyball (ranked second), 24.78% in basketball (ranked third), 14.09% in softball (ranked fourth), and 10.82% in table tennis (ranked fifth). This ranking highlights the popularity of specific sports among students, with badminton and volleyball being the top interests. The high interest in these sports suggests that students expect positive outcomes from participating in them, such as enjoyment, social interaction, and skill development (Martin et al., 2016; Cruz, 2022). Sports programs should prioritize these popular sports to meet student interests and maximize participation while promoting lesser-known sports to diversify students' sports experiences (Lagrio et al., 2017).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The results reveal significant insights into students' sports involvement, self-evaluation of sports skills, and experience in school sports competitions. With 65.91% of students playing sports, the data suggests a strong overall interest in sports activities. In contrast, the nearly equal split between students who consider themselves good at sports (44.15%) and those who do not (48.81%) highlights the need for supportive programs to enhance skills and confidence. The finding that

55.09% of students have participated in school sports competitions indicates a majority with some competitive experience, suggesting potential for further engagement through inclusive and accessible sports programs.

Moreover, the frequency of sports practice shows that while many students engage in sports regularly, a significant portion does so only occasionally, pointing to opportunities for increased engagement through improved access and motivation. Additionally, results reveal a high participation rate in local sports competitions but a notable decline at higher competition levels. This result highlights the need for more support and training for students aiming for advanced competition. Furthermore, the result identified the most popular sports among students, with badminton and volleyball leading the ranks, suggesting these sports could be prioritized in programs to maximize participation and meet student interests while promoting diversity in sports activities.

In conclusion, the survey data underscores the importance of understanding student interests and self-perceptions in sports to develop effective sports programs. The institution could enhance overall sports participation by aligning sports activities with students' expectations and providing support to build confidence and skills. The data highlights specific areas for improvement, such as increasing the frequency of sports practice, supporting higher-level competition participation, and addressing the needs of students who currently feel less competent in sports.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the survey results, the following recommendations are made: Firstly, to capitalize on students' high interest in badminton (43.02%) and volleyball (39.50%), the school could establish specialized training programs and regular sports clinics focused on skill development, teamwork, and competitive strategies. These initiatives aim to enhance students' enthusiasm and achieve positive outcomes. Alongside these efforts, regular training sessions and sports clinics could be organized for basketball, softball, and table tennis, which, though slightly less popular, still demonstrate significant interest levels among students, promoting participation and skill improvement across these sports.

Secondly, to diversify student sports experiences, intervention plans could be implemented to promote participation in lesser-known sports. The intervention can include organizing sports fairs, demo days, and introductory sessions to increase awareness and foster interest in these less popular sports. Furthermore, ensuring inclusivity and accessibility is crucial by adapting sports programs and facilities to accommodate students of all skill levels and physical abilities, fostering a welcoming environment for diverse participation.

Thirdly, enhancing social and competitive opportunities is key to fostering a vibrant sports culture on campus. Organizing regular intra- and inter-college sports competitions builds a sense of community, encourages social interaction, and provides platforms for students to showcase their skills across various sports. Additionally, creating more recreational and casual play opportunities such as open gym hours, intramural leagues, and drop-in sessions can cater to students interested in sports for enjoyment and social interaction beyond formal competition.

Fourthly, resources could be allocated towards upgrading existing sports facilities and equipment to support the growth and sustainability of sports programs. This investment ensures

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that facilities are safe, well-maintained, and capable of meeting the demand generated by high-interest sports activities. Furthermore, hiring qualified coaches and trainers who provide high-quality instruction and mentorship is essential for enhancing skill development and helping students achieve their personal sports-related goals.

Lastly, continuous assessment and impact evaluation are necessary for refining and improving sports programs. Conducting regular follow-up surveys and studies enables the college to monitor changes in student sports interests and participation levels, facilitating adjustments to effectively meet evolving student needs. Evaluating the impact of implemented sports programs on student engagement, physical health, mental well-being, and academic performance ensures that these initiatives are aligned with their intended outcomes and contribute positively to the overall student experience.

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